

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Organizational Performance: Exploring Future Research Avenue by Reviewing Relevant Literature

H.T.M. Quader Newaz^a, Farhana Newaz^b

^a Professor, DBA, International Standard University (ISU)

^b Adjunct Faculty, DBA, International Standard University (ISU)

ABSTRACT

The primary objective of this study is to conduct a comprehensive review of existing research on Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and its impact on organizational performance globally. This research focuses on the need to provide reliable evidence for researchers and professionals to address unresolved issues and emerging challenges in CSR and organizational performance research. The research utilized two prominent databases, Scopus, and PubMed, to gather relevant literature. A systematic literature review (SLR) methodology was employed to ensure a comprehensive, unbiased, and objective examination of existing research. There is an increasing number of research examining the relationship between CSR and organizational performance, indicating that the topic is of significant interest and relevance. However, many studies are concentrated within specific industries, which limits the generalizability of findings across different sectors. Research is often confined to geographic regions, leading to a potential lack of a global perspective. There is a need for more holistic research that can capture the impact of CSR across diverse industries and regions. Expanding studies to include different regions and countries provides a more comprehensive view of CSR's impact worldwide. The study also suggests that combining quantitative and qualitative methods could offer deeper insights and a more nuanced understanding of CSR's effects.

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1. Introduction

The landscape of corporate social responsibility (CSR) has been evolving significantly. Companies are increasingly expected to balance profit-making with positive societal impact, which drives greater emphasis on CSR and corporate governance. Achi, et al., (2022) highlighted that this dual obligation reflects a broader shift toward recognizing the value of

ethical practices and sustainable business operations. CSR encompasses a range of activities where companies commit to ethical practices that benefit society, such as environmental sustainability, fair labor practices, and community engagement. Corporate governance, on the other hand, refers to the frameworks and processes that ensure companies to operate in a transparent, accountable, and ethical manner. Scholars have indeed been deeply interested in CSR for decades, and its importance has only grown as stakeholders—ranging from customers to investors to employees—demand greater corporate accountability and social responsibility. This evolving focus not only informs business strategies but also influences the broader societal impacts of corporate actions.

A company's responsibilities extend beyond the financial returns it provides to its owners. All businesses, regardless of their size or industry, are increasingly encouraged to pursue social consciousness, economic competitiveness, and environmental sustainability (Bahta et al., 2021). Corporate social responsibility (CSR) as a non-financial performance indicator is associated with improved non-financial outcomes, such as enhanced risk management, increased employee job satisfaction, and greater innovation. Over time, organizations that prioritize CSR may benefit from a more positive work environment, enhanced ability to retain and attract top talent, and a culture of transparency and accountability. Institutions that invest significantly in human capital through CSR and sustainable practices are likely to develop cutting-edge solutions that address social and environmental challenges, thereby gaining a competitive edge. Despite its growing popularity across academic, business, and policy circles, there remain gaps in the literature regarding the nature, extent, and direction of the relationship between CSR and organizations' performance (Coelho et al., 2023).

The relationship between CSR and organizational performance is indeed a topic of ongoing debate and study. The diversity of findings in recent research underscores the complexity of this relationship. On one hand, studies such as those by Asiaei et al. (2023) demonstrate a positive correlation between CSR initiatives and improved organizational performance. This relationship could be attributed to factors like enhanced brand reputation, customer loyalty, and employee satisfaction resulting from effective CSR practices. On the other hand, research by Silva et al. (2023) and Adamkaite et al. (2023) documents cases where

no significant association or even a negative relationship between CSR and performance was observed. These studies might highlight potential drawbacks or inefficiencies in certain CSR practices, or the possibility that CSR investments do not always translate into immediate financial benefits.

The purpose of this study is to focus on evaluating recent studies from the past five years. By reviewing contemporary researches, this research aims to uncover existing gaps and inconsistencies in the relevant literature. These findings could provide insights into which aspects of CSR are most effective or where companies might be falling short. Insights from this study could help businesses to design more effective CSR strategies that align with their performance goals and address any shortcomings identified in previous research.

2. Reviewing of Relevant Literature

Recent studies suggest that improved CSR initiatives can positively impact financial performance. This impact occurs through enhanced brand reputation, increased employee engagement, and strengthened customer loyalty. Over time, these factors can lead to increased sales, better access to working and non-working capital, and reduced operating expenses. Asiaei et al. (2023) explored the relationship between CSR and performance measurement systems, as well as organizational performance. The study found that CSR is positively related to performance measurement systems and organizational performance. Additionally, CSR indirectly affects organizational performance through the mediating role of performance measurement systems. Nirino et al. (2022) investigated intellectual capital as a mediator in the CSR-intellectual capital relationship. Their results showed a partial mediation effect, indicating that CSR strategies positively influence the development of intellectual capital. This, in turn, enhances firms' competitive advantage and contributes to superior long-term financial performance. Bahta et al. (2021) investigated the relationship between CSR and the performance of SMEs. The study's findings contribute to understanding how CSR practices influence the performance outcomes of smaller enterprises in the Eritrean context.

The review of recent studies provides several essential insights into the impact of corporate social responsibility (CSR) on organizational

performance, with a particular focus on small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and various contextual factors. Wu et al. (2020) investigated the effect of financial distress and CSR on the corporate financial performance (CFP) of Chinese listed firms. The findings revealed that CSR significantly improves financial performance, with the effect being more pronounced for financially stable firms. Furthermore, state-owned enterprises exhibit a stronger positive relationship between CSR and CFP, indicating a more pronounced mutually beneficial scenario where both CSR and financial performance are enhanced. The impact of corporate social responsibility (CSR) on various sectors and organizational outcomes has been examined in several recent studies, highlighting how CSR influences financial performance across different contexts and industries. Hou et al. (2019) explored the impact of CSR on the financial performance of creative industries, including publishing, broadcasting, and film and television. The regression analysis demonstrated that CSR has a significant positive impact on the financial performance of these industries. Content media-related enterprises were identified as leaders in performance growth, suggesting that CSR initiatives are particularly effective in enhancing financial outcomes within the creative sector. Sasmito et al. (2023) investigated the effects of various factors, including entrepreneurship, CSR, organizational capability, competitive advantage, and external networking, on firm performance in Indonesia. The study found that CSR had a notable influence on firm performance; however, competitive advantage did not significantly affect performance when CSR was regulated. This suggests that while CSR is an essential factor in enhancing firm performance, its impact may be insignificant when competitive advantage is controlled or regulated.

Adamkaite et al. (2023) examined the impact of CSR on the financial performance of nine energy companies in Lithuania. The findings revealed a firm but neutral relationship between CSR and financial performance. This suggests that while CSR activities are present and potentially influential, they do not have a significant or clear-cut effect on the financial outcomes of energy companies. In this context. Muñoz et al. (2020) explored the impact of CSR on the performance of wineries in Spain. Although the specific results of this study are not detailed here, it generally contributes to understanding how CSR practices influence

performance within the wine industry. Fahad and Busru (2021) similarly focused on the effect of CSR disclosure on firm performance in India, considering both profitability and firm value. The results indicated a tendency for CSR disclosure to impact firm value and profitability negatively. Among the different types of disclosures, environmental and social disclosure scores had the most substantial negative influence. This suggests that in the Indian context, extensive CSR disclosure, particularly regarding environmental and social issues, might be associated with adverse financial outcomes.

The results challenge the commonly held belief that companies engaging in corporate social responsibility (CSR) achieve better performance. Instead, the data reveal that wineries with more environmentally conscious practices tend to be less profitable, and no significant relationship is found between CSR and performance for these companies. Supporting these findings, Garg and Gupta (2020) examined the performance of public and private sector firms in India under the mandatory CSR spending regime. Their findings indicate that public sector firms adhering to the mandatory CSR spending requirements exhibit lower performance. Additionally, there is no notable performance difference between private sector firms that comply with the CSR spending requirement and those that do not.

3. Research Design: Methods, and Techniques

The study employed a systematic review of published research on corporate social responsibility (CSR) and organizational performance. Tranfield et al. (2003) and Rahman et al. (2024) suggested that systematic reviews are essential tools for fostering discussion and sharing scholarly findings from various researchers. Furthermore, Manatos et al. (2017) defined a systematic review as a method for locating, evaluating, and analyzing previously published contributions concerning a specific research question. The main steps involved in conducting a systematic review include planning the review, conducting the review, and reporting and disseminating the results.

This study investigated the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and organizational performance. The research adopted the approach of Tranfield et al. (2003), which outlined organizing the study, conducting reviews, and reporting and

disseminating findings. The present study employed this approach because the approach of Tranfield et al. (2003) is trustworthy, transparent, and unbiased. To ensure a comprehensive review, a detailed search strategy was developed. Search terms such as "corporate social responsibility and organizational performance," "impact of corporate social responsibility on organizational performance," and "corporate social responsibility on performance" were used across two databases: Scopus and PubMed Scholar. These terms were chosen to capture a broad range of relevant articles related to the topic.

4. Techniques of Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion and exclusion criteria are crucial for systematic reviews as they ensure that the studies included are relevant, of high quality, and provide valuable insights into the research question (Anneke et al., 2008). These criteria typically cover a range of factors: (i) Publication Date: To ensure that the review includes the most recent and relevant research, studies are often restricted to a specific date range. (ii) Study Design: Only studies with specific designs (e.g., randomized controlled trials, cohort studies) are included to ensure methodological rigor and comparability. (iii) Sample Size: Studies included based on minimum sample size requirements to ensure statistical power and reliability of results. (iv) Relevance: Studies address the research question directly to contribute meaningful evidence. Additionally, the methodological quality of the included studies needs to be assessed using a checklist or quality assessment tool (Anneke et al., 2008).

Assessing methodological quality helps to ensure that the studies included in the review are credible and meet specific standards, ultimately contributing to the reliability and validity of the review's conclusions. By carefully selecting studies based on these criteria, systematic reviews aim to provide a comprehensive and accurate answer to the research question. For this systematic review, the inclusion and exclusion criteria were specifically designed to ensure the studies selected were both relevant and high-quality, particularly concerning the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and firm performance. These criteria were applied followed by the below-mentioned inclusion criteria: (i) Publication Date: Studies published between 2019 and 2023 were included to capture the most recent and

relevant research on CSR and firm performance, (ii) Language: Only studies written in English were considered to ensure accessibility and consistency in the review process, (iii) Database Availability: Studies had to be available in Scopus and PubMed databases, which are reputable sources for academic research. The exclusion criteria are: (iv) Industry or Country Focus: Studies focusing on industries or countries outside the scope of this review were excluded to maintain relevance to the specific context of the review's objectives. Using these criteria, the review included a total of 45 studies.

These selected studies were expected to provide valuable insights into the relationship between CSR and firms' performance, aligning with the review's objectives and contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the topic. By adhering to these criteria, the review aimed to ensure that the included studies were of high methodological quality and directly relevant to the research questions, thus enhancing the validity and reliability of the findings. The selected studies offer valuable insights into the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and firm performance. They help to clarify how CSR initiatives impact both financial and non-financial performance indicators.

5. Findings and Analysis

Table 1 shows that a significant majority of the studies, 90% (40 out of 45), found a positive relationship between CSR and organizational performance. This indicates a strong consensus among researchers that CSR activities tend to enhance performance outcomes. 8% (4 studies) did not find a positive significant relationship, and 2% (1 study) found the relationship to be neutral (please see Table 1). These findings suggest that CSR might not always lead to improved performance and the effect might be context-dependent. The studies that did not identify a positive relationship often were focused on specific industries such as energy, banking, construction, and hospitality, indicating that the impact of CSR on performance might vary significantly across different sectors. The unique challenges or characteristics of these industries might influence the effectiveness of CSR initiatives. Studies with negative or neutral results came from countries like Bangladesh, Pakistan, and Iran. This underscores the need for more localized research to better understand how CSR influences performance within specific national contexts, and to prevent the overgeneralization of findings across diverse economic and cultural environments.

Table 1 – Summary of Corporate Social Responsibility and Organizational Performance

No	Database	Country	Year	Sector	Method	Author	Relationship between CSR and Performance
1.	Scopus and PubMed	USA	2023	Hospitality Industry	Quantitative	Choi and Park (2022)	Yes
2.	Scopus and PubMed	UK and Spain	2023	Construction Industry	Quantitative	Silva et al. (2023)	Yes
3.	Scopus and PubMed	Lithuania	2023	Construction Industry	Quantitative	Adamkaite et al. (2023)	Yes
4.	Scopus and PubMed	Germany	2022	Listed on Stock Exchange	Quantitative	Velte (2022)	Yes
5.	Scopus and PubMed	UK, and Italy	2023	Listed on Stock Exchange	Quantitative	Franzoni et al. (2021)	Yes
6.	Scopus and PubMed	Italy	2023	SMEs	Quantitative	Nirino et al., (2022)	Yes
7.	Scopus and PubMed	Finland	2023	Listed on Stock Exchange	Literature Review	Maury (2022)	Yes
9.	Scopus and PubMed	Canada	2022	Banking Sector	Quantitative	Hashem (2023)	Yes
10.	Scopus and PubMed	Spain	2021	Multinational Corporations (MNCs)	Quantitative	Singh et al. (2023)	Yes
11.	Scopus and PubMed	Spain	2023	Agri-Food Companies	Quantitative	Martos-Pedrero (2023)	Yes
12.	Scopus and	USA	2021	Energy Sector	Quantitative	Adamkaite et al.	Yes

	PubMed					(2023)	
13.	Scopus and PubMed	Romania	2019	Listed on Stock Exchange	Qualitative	Asiaei et al. (2022)	Yes
14.	Scopus and PubMed	Turkey	2019	Tourism and Hospitality Industry	Quantitative	Nirino et al., (2022)	Yes
15.	Scopus and PubMed	USA	2022	Tourism and Hospitality Industry	Quantitative	Velte (2022)	Yes
16.	Scopus and PubMed	Spain	2023	Hospitality Industry	Literature Review	Goffi et al. (2022)	Yes
17.	Scopus and PubMed	China	2022	SMEs	Quantitative	Sarwar et al. (2022).	Yes
18.	Scopus and PubMed	India	2023	Different Organizations	Quantitative	Choi and Park (2022)	Yes
19.	Scopus and PubMed	Taiwan	2022	Natural Resources Sector	Quantitative	Babajee et al. (2022)	Yes
20.	Scopus and PubMed	Korea	2023	Banking Sector	Quantitative	Maury (2022)	Yes
21.	Scopus and PubMed	Vietnam	2022	Public and Private Firms	Quantitative	Achi et al. (2022)	Yes
22.	Scopus and PubMed	Pakistan	2023	Banking Sector	Quantitative	Al-Shammari (2022)	Yes
23.	Scopus and PubMed	Bangladesh	2020	Different Organizations	Quantitative	Franzoni et al. (2021)	Neutral
25.	Scopus and PubMed	Indonesia	2021	Different Organisations	Quantitative	Radu and Smaili (2021)	Yes
26.	Scopus and	Vietnam	2023	Nonfinancial Public	Quantitative	Liu and Lu (2021)	Yes

	PubMed			Firms			
27.	Scopus and PubMed	China	2022	Different Organisations	Quantitative	Bahta et al. (2021)	Yes
28.	Scopus and PubMed	Pakistan	2023	Hospitality Industry	Quantitative	Yeon (2021)	Yes
29.	Scopus and PubMed	Indonesia	2022	Banking Sector	Quantitative	Andayani (2021)	Yes
30.	Scopus and PubMed	China and Itali	2023	Multinational Corporations (MNCs)	Quantitative	Hunjra et al. (2021).	Yes
31.	Scopus and PubMed	Itali and Rusia	2023	Agri-Food Companies	Quantitative		Yes
32.	Scopus and PubMed	Iran	2022	Energy Sector	Quantitative	Asiaei et al. (2023)	No
33.	Scopus and PubMed	Pakistan	2021	Listed on Stock Exchange	Quantitative	Úbeda-García et al. (2021)	Yes
34.	Scopus and PubMed	Indonesia	2023	Tourism and Hospitality Industry	Quantitative	Fahad and Busru (2021)	Yes
35.	Scopus and PubMed	Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore,	2022	Tourism and Hospitality Industry	Quantitative	Okafor et al. (2021).	No
36.	Scopus and PubMed	Portugal	2021	Hospitality Industry	Quantitative	Devie et al. (2020)	No
37.	Scopus and PubMed	Mauritius	2022	SMEs	Quantitative	Muñoz et al. (2020).	Yes
38.	Scopus and PubMed	Eritrea	2023	Different Organizations	Quantitative	Miller et al. (2020)	Yes

39.	Scopus and PubMed	Nigeria	2023	Natural Resources Sector	Quantitative	Chijoke- Mgbame et al. (2020).	Yes
40.	Scopus and PubMed	Eritrea	2023	Banking Sector	Quantitative	Vu et al. (2020).	No
41.	Scopus and PubMed	Taiwan	2022	Multinational Corporations (MNCs)	Literature Review	Wu et al. (2020)	Yes
42.	Scopus and PubMed	India	2022	Agri-Food Companies	Quantitative	Pham and Tran (2020)	Yes
43.	Scopus and PubMed	Pakistan	2023	Energy Sector	Quantitative	Bhuiyan et al. (2020).	No
44.	Scopus and PubMed	Spain	2022	Listed on Stock Exchange	Quantitative	Garg and Gupta (2020).	
45.	Scopus and PubMed	Turkey	2023	Tourism and Hospitality Industry	Quantitative	Tulcanaza-Prieto et al. (2020).	Yes

(Source: Reviewing Scopus and PubMed Indexed Articles, 2024)

In this context, it can also be attested that more focused research is needed within specific industries to understand the nuanced effects of CSR. This could help in tailoring CSR strategies more effectively to different sectors. The U.S. led in the number of studies conducted, reflecting a high level of interest or a rich research environment regarding CSR and organizational performance in this region. Spain follows with a notable number of studies, indicating a regional focus on understanding the CSR-performance relationship in the European context. Both China and India show substantial research activity, reflecting the importance of CSR in rapidly developing economies with significant business activity and social impact. The overwhelming use of quantitative methods (93% of the studies) indicates a preference for numerical data and statistical analysis to measure the impact of CSR on performance. This approach provides measurable and generalizable results, which is useful for establishing trends and testing hypotheses. Literature reviews are less common but essential for synthesizing existing research and identifying gaps. They offer a comprehensive overview of the field but do not provide new empirical data. The use of qualitative methods was very limited (2% of the studies), suggesting a lesser emphasis on in-depth, descriptive analysis of CSR's impact. The limited use of qualitative methods suggests an opportunity to explore this area further. Qualitative research could uncover deeper insights into the mechanisms through which CSR influences performance and provide a context-specific understanding that quantitative methods might overlook. Combining quantitative and qualitative methods could offer a more comprehensive view, leveraging the strengths of both approaches to better understand CSR and performance relationships.

6. Discussion

The study aimed to review systematically relevant literature on CSR and organizational performance in Bangladesh and beyond. The research identified the existing status of CSR vis-à-vis organizational performance, adopted methodology, explored variables included for the study, identified scopes as to sectors and areas of study, and examined other major selected factors. In such a context, this discussion section reviews these factors, and findings systematically along with shortcomings, and gaps that were revealed.

Based on the review of 45 research articles, 32 studies found a positive relationship between CSR and organizational performance. This suggests that, in many cases, engaging in CSR activities is associated with improvements in various performance metrics for organizations. The review indicates a growing body of research examining the link between CSR and organizational performance. Despite the positive findings, there were some notable gaps in the literature. Specifically, more research is needed to explore additional variables that might mediate or moderate the relationship between CSR and performance. For instance, factors such as organizational culture, industry type, or stakeholder expectations could play significant roles in shaping this relationship. Recent research in fact has produced inconsistent and sometimes ambiguous results, highlighting the necessity for further studies to clarify these discrepancies and better understand the nature of the CSR performance link.

The review also reveals that CSR and performance evaluation studies are concentrated in a limited number of countries. For example, in Africa, only three countries (Mauritius, Nigeria, and Eritrea) have been represented in recent studies. In comparison, fewer than 10 countries in Asia have contributed to this body of research over the past five years. This limited geographic representation suggests that globally, the research on CSR is unevenly distributed. Future research thus needs to focus on incorporating this gap to a more globally representative and more comprehensive array of mediating variables to gain a more comprehensive understanding of how CSR influences organizational performance. In other words, there is a need for more studies across diverse geographic regions to provide a global perspective on CSR's impact. Research in underrepresented regions could offer valuable insights and contribute to a more balanced understanding of the CSR-performance relationship. Therefore, addressing the inconsistencies and ambiguities in current research is crucial. Future studies should aim for more robust and systematic methodologies to provide more precise insights into the dynamics of CSR and organizational performance.

The study highlights important considerations regarding the relevance and generalizability of research findings as to the relationship between

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and organizational performance. The relevance of CSR research is underscored by the variability in findings across different countries. For instance, in India, the review found mixed results: two out of four studies showed no significant relationship between CSR and organizational performance, while the other two did. Similarly, studies from Lithuania and Bangladesh reported no discernible relationship. This variability indicates that findings from one country may not be universally applicable, underscoring the importance of contextual factors in CSR research. Many studies with neutral or non-significant results were sector-specific. This suggests that the relationship between CSR and organizational performance may vary significantly across different industries. It indicates a need for further research to explore how sector-specific factors influence this relationship.

The review reveals a methodological imbalance in the current research on CSR and organizational performance. Out of 45 studies, only one employed a qualitative approach, while two were review studies from Germany and Australia. The overwhelming majority of studies relied on quantitative methods. This skew towards quantitative research may limit the depth and contextual understanding of CSR's impact. In such a backdrop it seems that there is a need for a more balanced approach to research methodologies. Incorporating qualitative methods, case studies, and mixed-method approaches could provide richer insights and a more nuanced understanding of CSR's effects on organizational performance. Future research should account for regional and sector-specific differences in studying CSR and organizational performance. Comparative studies across different countries and industries could help clarify how and why the relationship varies. The review shows that most studies have been conducted in listed companies. This means that small companies that would like to implement CSR but cannot go public due to the time and cost involved are not covered by these studies. The results also show that other relevant sectors such as transportation, health care, and other manufacturing sectors, have not been included and are therefore under-researched in terms of CSR. This is consistent with some studies that have found that the RMG sector or other organizations have

received very little research attention despite its critical role in the global economy (Yangailo, 2023; Yangailo, 2023a,2023b).

7. Importance of Bridging the Identified Gaps

Addressing the inconsistencies in the literature on the relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and organizational performance, is crucial for advancing our understanding of this complex dynamic. One of the primary ways to achieve this is by integrating mediating variables into future research. Mediating variables, which can either strengthen, weaken, or negate the relationship between an independent variable (such as CSR) and a dependent variable (like organizational performance), are essential for unraveling the nuances of how CSR initiatives impact performance. For instance, factors such as organizational culture, leadership style, or resource availability might play significant roles in determining the effectiveness of CSR efforts. In fact, the varying impact of CSR across different industries, driven by distinct market dynamics and consumer expectations, underscores the need for context-specific studies. By identifying and examining these mediating variables, researchers can better explain the mixed findings in the literature, thereby enabling more tailored CSR strategies that are aligned with specific organizational or regional contexts.

Quantitative research methods, such as structural equation modeling (SEM) or hierarchical regression analyses, can be employed to empirically test the impact of these mediating variables. Based on preliminary findings and theoretical frameworks, researchers should develop hypotheses about how specific mediating variables might affect the CSR-performance relationship.

Moreover, incorporating mediating variables in future research could help clarify the causal mechanisms underlying the observed effects. Mediating variables can explain the relationship between independent and dependent variables by linking them within a causal pathway. Including both moderators and mediators in future studies would allow scholars to provide a more comprehensive and insightful understanding of the complex dynamics between CSR and organizational performance, rather than merely examining their direct relationship. Additionally, replicating studies across different countries and industries is crucial for

establishing the validity, generalizability, and reliability of research findings.

Many research studies have predominantly employed quantitative methods, which often focus narrowly on specific variables and overlook the nuanced experiences and perspectives of individuals. While both quantitative and qualitative research methods have their respective strengths and limitations, they can be highly complementary when used together. To enhance the robustness of research findings, future studies should adopt a balanced approach that integrates various research methods. This mixed-methods approach, leveraging triangulation, would enable researchers to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between CSR and organizational performance.

A qualitative research approach allows researchers to explore ideas and experiences that are challenging to quantify, offering a deeper understanding of the human experience. Through qualitative methods, researchers can gather rich, detailed data about individuals and situations. The close relationship between participants and researchers in qualitative studies also enables participants to directly influence the research outcomes. Understanding the contextual complexities and diverse stakeholder perspectives within the CSR-performance interaction is crucial. Academic discourse often oversimplifies the impact of CSR, neglecting the subtle influences of contextual factors such as the regulatory environment (Mares, 2010). Furthermore, examining the local context in detail provides valuable insights into the various factors affecting the impact of CSR on firm performance. This approach allows researchers to develop a more accurate and context-specific understanding, tailored to different situations. Thus, adopting a balanced research approach, incorporating both qualitative and quantitative methods, is essential. This combined approach can address the limitations of using a single method and provide a more comprehensive view of the relationship between CSR and organizational performance.

8. Conclusion, and Limitations of the Study

The study underscores the importance of addressing the existing research gaps to gain a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between CSR and organizational performance. This research clearly shows that there has been an increase in research, but the focus has been narrowed,

and limited to specific industries and countries. By broadening the scope of research to include diverse sectors and regions, and incorporating a variety of methodologies, researchers can contribute to a more nuanced understanding of CSR's impact on firm performance. The methodology and analysis steps provided in this study offer a framework for conducting future research, helping to identify and address gaps in the literature. Given the dynamic nature of the business environment, it is crucial to continuously explore how CSR practices influence organizational performance to develop effective strategies that align with contemporary challenges and opportunities.

Acknowledging and addressing the limitations of a study is crucial for enhancing the robustness and credibility of research findings. The literature review was conducted using Scopus and PubMed database sources. While these are comprehensive databases, relying on just two sources may limit the scope of the literature reviewed. Other databases might contain valuable studies not indexed by these platforms. Future research should include a broader range of academic databases such as Google Scholar, Semantic Scholar, Web of Science, JSTOR, and ProQuest. These databases often offer access to peer-reviewed journals, conference proceedings, and grey literature that might not be available in Scopus and PubMed. Using databases that cater to specific fields (e.g., business, social sciences, environmental studies) can provide a more nuanced view of the literature. For instance, databases like Business Source Complete or ABI/INFORM might yield industry-specific insights.

Another limitation is that the systematic literature review focused exclusively on articles published in English. This may exclude valuable research published in other languages, potentially skewing the findings and overlooking significant contributions from non-English-speaking regions. Future research should explore databases and resources that index non-English literature. For example, databases like the Chinese National Knowledge Infrastructure (CNKI), JSTOR Global, or Latin American and Caribbean Health Sciences (LILACS) could be valuable. Translation services or consultation with bilingual experts can be utilized to access and understand relevant articles published in other languages,

ensuring that important findings from non-English sources are not overlooked.

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Declaration of Interests

We, the authors of this research manuscript, declare that we have no financial interest. We have provided written consent to publish the paper in this journal.

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